

The Hidden Labour of Digitalization at Home

Making the 'costs' of digital housekeeping visible

Background and social context

- More and more households use smart technologies, but hardly anyone talks about the work behind them.
- Digital innovations are reshaping the way we balance work, care and family life.
- We spend most of leisure and non-paid working time at home. The home is at the core of our private lives, and it is crucial for recreation, partnership and family.
- Our society must be aware of the challenges triggered by digital transformation technologies at home.
- The Digital Housekeeping is a new type of domestic work that must be taken into account.

What is digital housekeeping?

Digital **housekeeping** is essential like **physical chores** but often **invisible**.

Where does digital housekeeping come into play?

In remote work:

Managing the digital workspace at home, including clearing, sorting, preparing, provisioning, and troubleshooting.

In smart homes:

Setting up and maintaining connected devices, managing security updates, troubleshooting IoT systems, and organizing digital subscriptions.

In digital data management at home:

Organizing and maintaining personal digital archives, including sorting and storing pictures or videos in folders or clouds, curating, editing, deleting, and transferring digital data between devices.

In family & household administration:

Managing digital calendars, online shopping accounts, cloud storage, and shared devices among family members.

In home energy management:

Overseeing solar panels, electric vehicle charging, battery storage, and energy platforms.

Why is it relevant?

Time Costs

Digital housekeeping is essential for smooth processes in paid work, the energy transition, and family care work. It requires appropriate recognition (e.g., in terms of working time recording and remuneration).

Technical Skills

Digital housekeeping demands specific technical skills and appropriate support (e.g., through further training).

Workload

The volume of tasks at home is growing due to digitalization, leading to increased stress.

Social Impoverishment

Screen-based work is increasing, social relationships are increasingly mediated by technology, and the boundaries between leisure and work are becoming blurred.

Surveillance Risk

Digital technologies at home can enable the monitoring and control of work performance, raising concerns about privacy, autonomy and abuse.

Gender Dimension

Digital housekeeping is often managed by men, reinforcing control over the home and potentially disempowering women (e.g., through surveillance, exclusion from tech use, or energy policing).

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